

Functionalized chelating resins for selective sorption of metal ions : an overview

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The design and synthesis of chelating resins for the selective separation and determination of target metal ions from multi-component solutions will continue to be an important area of research into the 21st century. Taking into account the importance of the subject, this review is focused on the synthesis, characterization and the applications of the chelating resins in the preconcentration, separation and determination of trace metals from different complex samples. It is evident from critical review on this topic that major work has been carried out on separation of transition metals present in environmental samples. Analytical figures-of-merit of the determination of different elements have also been examined. There are limited reports on the speciation of metals by using this technique. The article involves the discussions on 130 references covering the period 1980 to 2002.

1. Introduction

The analyses of trace elements in natural and waste water, biological, industrial and geological samples in complex mixtures are the challenging problem in analytical chemistry. The heavy metals such as Pb, Cd, Hg etc. are toxic to most organisms¹. The production of nuclear weapons has also resulted in dangerous waste problems. Burning of coal in power station, industries or other combustion units emits particulate matter that carries hazardous substances like toxic metals. In addition, there is a growing interest to recover the precious metals due to both environmental and economic reasons^{2,3}. Thus accurate determination of trace elements, precious metals, lanthanide etc. are important from the environmental as well as ecological and economical points of view. In this connection one important problem arises that the target elements present in environment are in so low concentration that many sophisticated instruments fail to measure accurately. The rapid development of electronic instrumentation has created powerful analytical tools but it can give erroneous result due to the presence of matrix elements. To obtain reliable data, the best course is to separate the analytes of interest from the matrix constituents and to determine them in isolated state. Thus preconcentration and separation followed by analysis is mandatory particularly when analyte is present at ng ml^{-1} level. Solvent extraction⁴ and ion exchange resin⁵ are the two most common methodologies for the preconcentration and separation of trace elements from various matrices. Solvent extraction is inefficient due to requirement of large volume of solvent which may create health hazard problem. Solid phase ex-

traction using chelating resins is the method of choice due to its high separation efficiency, good reproducibility of retention parameters and high sensitivity. They have found widespread applications in the enrichment of metals from various sources.

Chelating resin is basically an organic copolymer containing donor atoms which can successfully interact with the metal ions through coordinate bond whereas polymer backbone makes them more efficient by offering large surface area. It has some advantages over solvent extraction such as higher preconcentration factor, better efficiency, greater reproducibility and greater simplicity in handling and transfer⁶.

The preparation of such chelating resins were carried out in two different ways, first of which involves the physical adsorption of chelating ligand on the support such as polystyrene-divinyl benzene whereas the second one involves the incorporation of such ligand through covalent linking into the matrix. The adsorbed resin has little stability in high ionic strength as well as in organic solvent. The partial elution of the chelating ligand with the high concentration of perchloric or hydrochloric acid makes the use of the column impossible for several sorption-elution process. Thus the functionalization of the chelating ligand is a promising technique. In recent years, the development of suitable functionalized chelating resin for trace metal preconcentration and separation provides a new impetus to extraction approach. Kantipuly *et al.*⁷ discussed the usefulness of the chelating polymers including some commercial resin based on polystyrene, silica gel, cellulose etc. in chemi-

cal analysis with special emphasis on uranium preconcentration. Bilba *et al.*⁸ and Garg *et al.*⁹ also focused the applications of chelating sorbents to various samples. Beauvais and Alexandratos¹⁰ reviewed the analytical applications of chelating resins in chemical analysis. However, detailed synthetic routes for the incorporation of active ligand into the polymeric matrix were not stated by them.

The aim of the present review is to document various synthetic methods of chelating polymers, characteristics and their applications in inorganic analysis. The source of this literature survey is the Chemistry Citation Index (1995-2002) and Chemical Abstract (1980-2002). Although it is difficult to refer all the papers published in this area, the enlisted bibliography of the reviewed papers could give a coverage of the advancement of the topic up to date. Fig. 1 shows the number of published paper during the last 20 years or so as a function of the year of their publication. It is evident that the scientific literature concerning this topic has been increasing year by year with an average of 6 publications per year.

Fig. 1. Development of the literature published about functionalized chelating resins during last twenty years.

2. Methods of preparation

In order to prepare the ion selective chelating resin, the active ligands and the method of linkage were the key factors. Various methods were used to incorporate a chelating ligand into polymeric matrix. They are classified into five

categories viz. incorporation through -N=N- linkage; incorporation through -CH₂- spacer; incorporation through amide linkage; by esterification reaction; by polycondensation method.

2.1. Incorporation through -N=N- linkage :

2.1.1. Incorporation of chelating ligand containing -OH groups : The main synthetic route of chelating resins proves to be introduction of an active functional group into polymeric network by reaction of polymer. Davies *et al.*¹¹ first introduced *o*-hydroxy arsonic acid, kojic acid by -N=N- linkage through the steps shown in Scheme 1. In order to couple active ligand containing phenolic-OH group, strong bases like NaOH, KOH etc. were used because the *o*-hydrogen with respect to -OH group is less acidic in nature.

Scheme 1. Synthetic pathways of chelating resins through azo linkage.

Using this technique Ghosh *et al.* synthesized the resin containing 1-nitroso-2-naphthol¹² and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol¹³. Styra-Brajter and Zeotorzynska synthesized pyridyl azo resorcinol (PAR)¹⁴ containing chelating resin. Saxena *et al.* modified Amberlite XAD-2 by Alizarin red-S¹⁵, salicylic acid¹⁶, and pyrocatechol violet¹⁷. Lim *et al.*¹⁸ attempted to synthesize the resin containing thiazolylazophenol as the active ligand. *o*-Vaniline thiosemicarbazone anchored chelating resin was synthesized by Jain *et al.*¹⁹. Lee *et al.*²⁰ incorporated 4-(2-thiazolylazo)resorcinol (TAR) which acts as a terdentate ligand and forms 1 : 1 complexes with most metals. Other workers^{21,22} also used pyridylazo naphthol (PAN)²¹, 1-(2-thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (TAN)²² as functional groups. Tewari and Singh applied chromotropic acid²³, thiosalicylic acid²⁴, xylol orange²⁵, pyrocatechol²⁶ as chelating ligands. Kumar *et al.* described the functionalization of Amberlite XAD-2 with *o*-aminophenol²⁷, tiron²⁸, quinalizarin²⁹ and pyrogallol³⁰. Mondal *et al.* modified styrene-divinylbenzene (8%) by 2-naphthol-3,6- disulphonic acid³¹. Most of the workers characterized -N=N- linkage by the presence of a band in the region 1510–1519 cm⁻¹ in IR spectrum. The amount of ligand incorporated during the course of reaction was cal-

culated by elemental analyses. As the chelating resin contains a weak base functional group like phenolic-OH, it is expected that the sorption of metal will depend on the pH of the medium.

2.1.2. Incorporation of chelating ligand containing heterocyclic N-donor site : Heterocyclic N has a special affinity for class-b metals and by taking the advantages of this property several workers synthesized a large number of chelating resin having heterocyclic N atom. Chattopadhyay *et al.*³² and Das *et al.*³³ synthesized chelating resins functionalized respectively with imidazole and benzimidazole into styrene-divinylbenzene (8%). Using styrene-divinylbenzene (8%) Mondal *et al.* modified the same matrix by 6-mercaptopurine³⁴ whereas Banerjee *et al.*³⁵ synthesized the chelating resin having imidazole 4,5-dicarboxylic acid as an active group. Due to the presence of two electronegative N atoms in the imidazole moiety, C-2 hydrogen should be highly acidic and hence, in order to couple with diazonium salts, weaker bases like Na_2CO_3 may be used.

2.2. Incorporation through $-\text{CH}_2-$ spacer :

Another type of incorporating system of the chelating ligand into the polymeric network is based on $-\text{CH}_2-$ linkage. In this case polymer like styrene-divinylbenzene co-polymer was first chloromethylated and then allowed to react with the amine or thiol group of the chelating ligand resulting immobilized solid support which may carry various donor atoms (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Synthetic pathways of chelating resins through methylene linkage.

2.2.1. Incorporation through N-atom : Iminodiacetic acid³⁶ was the first example of such introduction into the polymer. Other ligands like thiourea³⁷, nitrosoresorcinol³⁸, thiazole and thiazoline³⁹, phenyl alanine⁴⁰, anthranilic acid azide⁴¹, triaethiol⁴², piperazin⁴³, were also incorporated. Liu⁴⁴ described the synthesis of chelating resin containing histidine moiety with four functional groups viz. carboxylic group, uncharged amine group and two nitrogens in the imidazole ring which are potential sites of coordination to

metal ions. Other workers have also been immobilized aminopyrazolone⁴⁵, lysine N^α, N^α -diacetic acid⁴⁶, 8-hydroxyquinoline⁴⁷, 1-(2-aminomethyl)piperazine⁴⁸, (*N*-5-formyl salicylidine)ethane⁴⁹, methyl urea⁵⁰ into the polymeric matrix. A ring opening reaction of cyclohexene oxide and sulfide by the amino group immobilized on a VBC/DVB co-polymer leads to the formation of a series of novel chelating resin⁵¹. Mondal *et al.* incorporated bis-(*o*-aminophenyl)disulfide⁵² and 1,2-bis-(*o*-aminophenylthio)ethane⁵³ on such matrix. Microwave assisted synthesis of the chelating resin was introduced first by Mondal *et al.* who modified chloromethylated polystyrene DVB (2%) with *o*-aminothiophenol S-acetic acid under a microwave irradiation for 45 min at 180 W power level⁵⁴ in stead of classical 40 h refluxing. The resin thus obtained was compared with resin obtained by classical heating in terms of yield, IR and elemental analyses and it was found that the products are identical. By using the same technique adenine anchored polystyrene DVB (2%)⁵⁵ was also synthesized by the same group of workers.

2.2.2. Incorporation through S-atom : The chloromethyl group not only reacts with primary or secondary amine but also with thiol group as evident by the linkage of thiomethyl⁵⁶, dithizone or dehydrodithizone⁵⁷ into the matrix. X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted to identify the chemical state of sulphur and oxygen in the resin matrix and physical state was measured by scanning electron microscope (SEM) by Saha *et al.*⁵⁶.

2.3. Incorporation through amide linkage :

Although amide linkage is acid sensitive but there are reports in which polymeric matrix was functionalized through this bond. Phillips and Fritz⁵⁸ was the pioneer in this field and they incorporated *N*-phenyl hydroxamic acid into the styrene divinylbenzene co-polymer by the general procedure shown in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3. Synthetic pathways of chelating resins through amide linkage.

The method was popular by the successful introduction of various ligands like tertiary aliphatic amide⁵⁹, acyl oxime⁶⁰, cystein⁶¹, 8-aminoquinoline⁶², thiosalicyl amide⁶³, benzoyl acetanilide⁶⁴, quinaldine acidamide⁶⁵, piconilamide⁶⁶, thiopropionamide⁶⁷, thioacetamide⁶⁸, mercaptoacetamide⁶⁹ into the polymeric matrix.

2.4. Incorporation through esterification reaction :

Moyer and Fritz⁷⁶ was the first to synthesize such a linkage by the reaction of polystyrene-DVB resin with propylene diaminotetraacetic acid (PDTA). A general route presented in Scheme 4 is used to incorporate various chelating groups.

Dev and Rao incorporated bicine⁷¹, bis-(*N,N'*-salicylidene)-1,3-propane diamine⁷², *N*-hydroxyethyl ethylenediamine⁷³ moieties through esterification reaction. Several workers introduced hexylthioglycolate⁷⁴, thioglycolate⁷⁵, 1-hydrazinophthalazine⁷⁶ into the solid moiety through Scheme 4. Macrocyclic ligands like crown ethers sometimes give interesting results because this type of ligand is specific for a particular element. The incorporation of 7-aza-1,4,10,13-tetrathia cyclohexadecane into poly(glycidylmethacrylate)⁷⁷ leads to such type of matrix which is very selective for noble metals.

Scheme 4. Synthetic pathways of chelating resins through ester linkage.

2.5. By polycondensation :

Sometimes chelating resins can be obtained by the polycondensation of monomeric active chelating ligand. In this way resins containing ethylenediamine⁷⁸, dithiocarbamate⁷⁹, 8-hydroxyquinoline 5-sulphonic acid⁸⁰, vinylphosphamic acid⁸¹, 1,1-vinylidenediphosphonic acid⁸², azacrown⁸³ have been synthesized. Alexandratos *et al.*⁸² characterized the resulting resin by solid state ³¹P NMR spectra. The peak at 27.5 ppm confirmed the presence of -PO₃H in the polymeric matrix. A ring opening-metathesis polymerization (ROMP) technique was described by Sinner *et al.*⁸⁴ for preparation of dipyriddyamide-functionalized polymer which may be used as a solid phase metal ion collector.

3. Physicochemical properties

3.1. Stability : The stability constant value of the complex formed by the interaction of donor atoms and metal ions in polymeric matrix is very useful for the optimization

of the retention process. Mechanical and chemical stabilities of a chelating resin depends on the synthetic method and matrix nature. Thus condensation polymers have poor chemical as well as mechanical stability. Crosslinked polymers with hydrophobic matrix are preferred because of their high chemical stability and mechanical strength.

3.2. Exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of chelating resin towards metal ions depends on the amount of the chelating ligand incorporated into the polymeric matrix as well as the nature of the donor atoms present in the active site. It was observed that a conventional ion exchange resin has higher exchange capacity than that of a chelating resin.

3.3. Kinetics : Kinetic property of a chelating resin mainly depends on the nature and degree of crosslinking of polymer. The sorbents with the best kinetic characteristics are those which have low degree of crosslinking. The sorption of metal ion on the resin is by particle-diffusion mechanism or by second order kinetics. According to Frost and Pearson⁸⁵ the sorption of metal ions with chelating resin follows second order kinetic and the rate law derived by Rieman and Tursue⁸⁶ is as follows :

$$\ln Z = 2kQ_0(Q_0 - Q_\alpha) t / Q_\alpha$$

$$\text{where } Z = [Q_t(Q_0 - 2Q_\alpha) + Q_0Q_\alpha] / Q_0(Q_\alpha - Q_t)$$

The rate constant, *k* is calculated from the slope, *S* given by

$$S = 2kQ_0(Q_0 - Q_\alpha) / Q_\alpha$$

where *Q_t* is the amount (mmole) of metal ion exchanged at time, *t*, *Q_α* is the maximum exchange capacity at equilibrium and *Q₀* is the amount of chelating resin in terms of mmole of Na⁺ exchanged after 24 h. A plot of ln *Z* versus *t* should be linear through zero for a second order exchange. Based on this equation Mondal *et al.*^{31,87} and Banerjee *et al.*⁸⁸ calculated the rate constant values for both Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI}.

4. Analytical applications

The selective sorption of certain elements in the presence of others, based on the different stabilities of the complexes formed by functional groups of the sorbents, has led to the use of these materials for selective preconcentration and separation of metal ions present in environmental, biological or industrial matrices.

The choice of an effective chelating resin and its application in analytical methodology is indicated by the physicochemical properties like polarizability, selectivity, exchange capacity, kinetics, stability characteristics of the poly-

mer. Akaiwa and Kawamoto⁸⁹ discussed the advantages of having synergistic agent on a chelating resin to enhance the sensitivity and separation of trace metals. The concept of hard and soft acid and base^{90,91} provides an important guideline for the selection of the method. Usually O, N, S (sometimes P) are present in the chelating resin which determine the ability to interact with the metal ions forming chelated ring. Functional groups of the chelating resin usually act as bases; oxygen containing functional groups are hard and sulfur containing groups are soft. Functional group with a basic nitrogen have an intermediate character.

The reader is invited to go through Table 1 for the analytical methodology for the separation of selected metal ions using functionalized chelating resins. It transpires that

separation of metals can be carried out (i) by azo functionalized resins having phenolic-OH group, heterocyclic N-donor atoms, (ii) resins anchored by $-CH_2-$ group, (iii) resins having amide linkage, (iv) esterified resins or (v) polycondensed resins. After separation, metals are usually analyzed by UV/Vis spectrophotometry or atomic absorption spectrometry techniques suitable for trace analysis. However, in some cases fluorimetry and radiochemical methods like NAA have also been used.

It is evident from Table 1 that major work has been carried out on separation of transition metals present in environmental samples. Outlines of the methodologies presented in selected papers are also discussed below.

Table 1. Analytical methodology for the separation of selected metal ions using functionalized chelating resins

Solid matrix	Active group	Metal studied	Instrumental technique	Applications	Ref.
PS-DVB	1-Nitroso-2-naphthol	Pd ^{II} , U ^{VI}	Spectrophotometry	Sea water	12
PS-DVB	1-Nitroso-2-naphthol	Hg ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , V ^V , Pd ^{II}	AAS	–	13
Amberlite XAD-2	Pyridylazoresorcinol	Ag ^I	On line AAS	Ore and alloy	14
Amberlite XAD-2	Alizarin red-S	Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	AAS	Well water	15
Amberlite XAD-2	Salicylic acid	Zn ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	"	"	16
Amberlite XAD-2	Pyrocatechol violet	Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Ni ^{II}	"	"	17
Amberlite XAD-16	Thiazolylazophenol	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Cu ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Mn ^{II}	Spectrophotometry	Sea water	18
Amberlite XAD-2	<i>o</i> -Vanillinthiosemi-carbazone	Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	AAS	River water	19
Amberlite XAD-2	<i>o</i> -Vanillinthiosemi-carbazone	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	ICP-AES, GF AAS	Monazite sand, standard geological materials	120
PS-DVB	4-(2-Thiazolylazo)resorcinol	Cu ^{II}	ICP-AES	Synthetic mixture	20
PS-DVB	4-(2-Thiazolylazo)resorcinol	U ^{VI}	"	"	92
Chloromethyl polystyrene	Phridylazo naphthol (PAN)	Au ^{III} , Cd ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cr ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Mn ^{II} , Pd ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	AAS	Tap. waste water, human urine, milk, ore	21
PS-DVB	1-(2-Thiazolylazo)-2 naphthol (TAN)	Zr ^{IV} , Hf ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	Spectrophotometry	–	22
Amberlite XAD-2	Chromotropic acid	Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	AAS	Well water	23
Amberlite XAD-4	Thiosalicylic acid	Cd ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	"	River water	24
Amberlite XAD-7	Xylenol orange	Cd ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	"	River water, pharmaceutical tablets	25

Table-1 (contd.)

Amberlite XAD-2	Pyrocatechol	Cd ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	AAS	Tap water, river water, vitamin tablets	26
Amberlite XAD-2	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	"	Well water	27
Amberlite XAD-2	Tiron	Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , UO ₂ ^{II}	Fluorimetry, AAS	Well water, pharma- ceutical tablets	28
Amberlite XAD-2	Quinalizarin	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Mn ^{II}	"	Well water, vitamin tablets	29
Amberlite XAD-2	Pyrogallol	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , U ^{VI}	AAS, Fluorimetry	Well water, river water, vitamin tablets	30
PS-DVB	2-Naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid	Cr ^{III} , Cr ^{VI}	AAS	Natural water	31
PS-DVB	Imidazolylazo	Hg ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	Tracer	Waste water	32
PS-DVB	"	Pd ^{II} , Ag ^I	"	Geological sample	93
PS-DVB	"	Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	AAS	Biological sample	94
PS-DVB	Benzimidazolylazo	Hg ^{II} , Ag ^I , Pd ^{II}	Tracer, Spectrophotometry	-	33
PS-DVB	6-Mercapto purine	Hg ^{II} , Ag ^I	AAS	Natural water, medicinal samples	34
PS-DVB	"	Cr ^{III} , Cr ^{VI}	"	Natural water	87
PS-DVB	"	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	"	Biological samples	95
PS-DVB	Imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid	V ^{IV} , V ^V	"	Waste water	35
PS-DVB	Imidazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid	Cr ^{III} , Cr ^{VI}	"	Natural water	88
PS	Iminodiacetic acid	Ca ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	Chelatometry	-	36
Aminoethyl PS-DVB	Thiourea	Ag ^I , Hg ^{II}	AAS	-	37
Chloromethyl PS-DVB	Nitrosoresorcinol	Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	Tracer	Synthetic mixtures	38
PS-DVB	Thiazole and thiazoline	Hg ^{II}	"	Sea water	39
PS	Phenyl alanine	Cu ^{II} , Hg ^{II}	AAS	"	40
PS	Anthranilic acid hydrazide	Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{II} , Rh ^{II} , Ru ^{II} , Os ^{VI} , Au ^{III} , Ag ^I	Spectrophotometry	Synthetic mixture	41
Poly(ethylacrylate)	Triazolethiol	Ag ^I , Hg ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	AAS, Tracer	Sea water	42
Phenol- formaldehyde resin	Piperazine	Cu ^{II}	AAS	-	43
Amberlite IRC-50	Histidine	Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Ag ^I , Au ^{III} , Fe ^{III}	Spectrophoto- metry, AAS	Natural water	44
Chloromethyl PS	Aminopyrazolone	Au ^{III} , Ag ^I , Pd ^{II} , Mn ^{II}	AAS	-	45
Chloromethyl PS	Lysine- <i>N</i> ^α , <i>N</i> ^α -diacetic acid	Trivalent hard metals	Spectrophotometry	-	46
Chloromethyl PS	"	Pt ^{III} , Nd ^{III}	"	-	107
Phenol- formaldehyde resin	8-Hydroxyquinoline	Cu ^{II}	On line AAS	Synthetic mixture	47

Table-1 (contd.)

PS	1-(2-Aminomethyl)piperazine	Au ^{III} , Ru ^{IV} , Os ^{IV} , Pt ^{IV} , Ir ^{IV}	Spectrophotometry	Synthetic mixture	48
Chloromethyl PS	(<i>N</i> -5-Formyl-salicylidine) ethane	Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	AAS	–	49
PVC-DVB	Methylthiourea, guanylthiourea, dithiocarbamate	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Ag ^I	”	–	50
Chloromethyl PS-DVB	Cyclohexene oxide and sulfide	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Ni ^{II}	”	Synthetic mixture	51
Chloromethyl PS	Bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulfide	As ^{III} , As ^V	HG-AAS	Polluted water	52
Chloromethyl PS	1,2-Bis-(<i>o</i> -aminophenylthio) ethane	Hg ^{II} , CH ₃ Hg ^I	”	Waste water	53
Chloromethyl PS	2-Aminothiophenyl- <i>S</i> acetic acid	Pb ^{II}	AAS	Road dust	54
Chloromethyl PS	Adenine	Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	”	Sludge	55
PS	Thiomethyl group	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	”	Natural water	56
Chloromethyl PS	Dithizone	Au ^{III} , Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Os ^{IV} , Ir ^{IV} , Ru ^{III} , Rh ^{III}	DCPES	Geological samples	57
Amberlite XAD-4	<i>N</i> -Phenylhydroxamic acid	Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Ti ^{IV} , Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	Colorimetry	–	58
Amberlite XAD-4	Tertiary aliphatic amide	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , Pd ^{II} , Au ^{III}	Spectrophotometry, ICP-AES	Uranium in uraninite and carnotite	59
PS-DVB	Acyloxime	Cu ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	Chelatometry	–	60
Polyacrylonitrile	Cysteine	Ag ^I , Hg ^{II} , Au ^{III} , Pt ^{IV}	Spectrophotometry	–	61
Poly(glycidylmethyl acrylate)	8-Aminoquinoline	Fe ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Mn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Au ^{III} , Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Hg ^{II}	”	–	62
PS-DVB	Thiosalicylamide	Pt ^{II}	”	–	63
PS-DVB	Benzoyl acetanilide	Ti ^{IV} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	Spectrophotometry	Ti in bauxite	64
PS-DVB	Quinaldenic acid amide	Hg ^{II}	CV-AAS	Waste water	65
PS-DVB	”	Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{IV}	Spectrophotometry	Kongsberg silver	98
Amberlite IRC-50	”	Au ^{III} , Ag ^I	”	Ore and rock samples	99
Amberlite IRC-50	”	U ^{VI}	”	U in ore	100
PS-DVB	Picolinamide	Hg ^{II}	”	Natural, waste water	66
Poly(vinyl chloride)	Thiopropionamide	Noble metals	ICP-AES	–	67
Amberlite IRC-50	Thioacetamide	Cu ^{II}	Spectrophotometry	Ore and alloy	68
Polyethyleneimine	Mercaptoacetamide	As ^{III} , As ^V	DCPES	–	69
PS	PTDA-4	Cu ^{II} , U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV}	Spectrophotometry	Sea water	70
Amberlite XAD-4	Bicine	Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Hg ^{II}	AAS	Sea water	71
Amberlite XAD-4	Bis-(<i>N,N'</i> -salicylidene) 1,3-propanediamine	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Cr ^{III}	”	Natural water	72
Amberlite XAD-4	<i>N</i> -Hydroxyethyl-ethylenediamine	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , Cr ^{III}	”	Synthetic mixture	73
Amberlite XAD-4	Hexylthioglycolate	Ag ^I , Hg ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , Ac ^{III}	Spectrophotometry	–	74
Amberlite XAD-4	Thioglycolate	Ag ^I , Hg ^{II} , Sn ^{IV} , Sb ^{III} , Au ^{III} , Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II} , UO ₂ ^{II}	AAS, spectrophotometry	Hg ^{II} in simulated chloroalkali brine	75
Amberlite XAD-4	1-Hydrazinophthalazine	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Pb ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Cr ^{III}	AAS	Synthetic mixture	76

Table-1 (contd.)

Poly(glycidyl-methacrylate)	7-Aza-1,4,10,13-tetrathia-cyclohexadecane	Ag ^I , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	AAS	–	77
Polymerised	Ethylenediamine	Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	Chelatometry	–	78
Polymerised	Dithiocarbamate	Fe ^{III} , V ^V , Cr ^{VI} , W ^{VI} , Ti ^{IV} , Th ^{IV}	ICP-AES	–	79
Polymerised	8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid	Zn ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	AAS	–	80
Polymerised	Vinylphosphoramidic acid	Dy ^{III} , Ho ^{III} , Er ^{III} , Yb ^{III}	ICP-AES	Waste water	81
Polyacrylonitrile	1,1-Vinylidenedi-phosphonic acid	Eu ^{III}	AES	Aqueous solution	82
Polymerised	Azacrown and azathiocrown	Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Ag ^I , Au ^{III}	Spectrophotometry	–	83
Polymerised	Dipyridylamide	Hg ^{II} , Pd ^{II}	ICP-AES	Synthetic mixture	84
Poly(2-chloro-ethoxymethylirane)	Amino and mercapto group	Hg ^{II} , Au ^{III} , Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Ag ^I , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	AAS	Environmental samples	96
Phenol-formaldehyde resin	Diethylenetriamine-pentaacetic acid	In ^{IV} , Th ^{IV}	Spectrophotometry	Tap and sea water	97
DVB	Vinyl pyridine	Cu ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	Tracer, AAS	Sea water	101
Polymerised	Dithiocarbamate	Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	AAS	Fresh water	102
PS-DVB	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyaldehyde	Mn ^{II} , Mg ^{II} , Ca ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	"	–	103
PS-DVB	Thiosemicarbazide	Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Ru ^{III} , Rh ^{III} , Ir ^{III}	Spectrophotometry	–	104
Polymerised	Hydroxamic acid	Zn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II}	AAS	–	105
PS	β -Hydroxydithiocinnamic acid	Ag ^I , Au ^{III} , Hg ^{II} , Pt ^{IV}	Spectrophotometry	–	106
Polyacrylic acid	Amidoxin	U ^{VI}	Spectrophotometry	Sea water	108
Polyacrylic acid	Amidoxin	Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II}	NAA, AAS	Sea water	109
Amberlite IRC-50	Benzoylphenylhydroxyl amine	Ti ^{IV} , Fe ^{III} , Al ^{III}	"	Ti in clay and bauxite	110
Amberlite IRC-50	Benzoylphenylhydroxyl amine	Zr ^{IV} , Hf ^{IV}	Spectrophotometry	Synthetic mixture	111
Poly(vinylbenzene)	Oxime	Fe ^{III}	AAS	–	112
Polyacrylonitrile	Aminoguanidine	Cu ^{II}	Spectrophotometry	–	113
Polyacrylonitrile	Aminoguanidine	Au ^{III}	"	–	114
PS	Methylamino glucitol	Cu ^{II} , Ag ^I , Au ^{III}	"	–	115
Chloromethyl PS	8-Hydroxyquinoline	Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	AAS	Sea water	116
PS-DVB	Diethylenetriamine	Transition metal ions	Spectrophotometry	–	117
PS-DVB	1,2,4,5-Tetrazine	Pd ^{II} , Au ^{III}	DCPES	–	118
PS-DVB	Methylenephosphonic acid	Mo ^{VI}	"	–	119
Poly(vinylpyridine)	Dithizone	Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{II} , Au ^{III}	AAS	–	121
Polymerised	Chloromethyl thiirane	Au ^{III} , Ag ^I	Spectrophotometry	–	122
Polyacrylonitrile	Triazolthione	Rh ^{III} , Ru ^{IV} , Pd ^{II} , Ir ^{IV}	"	–	123
PS-DVB	2-Mercaptoethylamine	Au ^{III} , Pt ^{IV} , Ag ^I , Pd ^{II} , Hg ^{II}	"	–	124
PVC-DVB	Aminothiophosphonate	Cd ^{II} , Ni ^{II}	AAS	–	125
Polymalonamide	Aminomethylphosphonate	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II}	"	–	126

Table-1 (contd.)

PS-DVB (2%)	Phenylphosphonic acid	Cu ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Eu ^{III}	ASS	–	127
Polyacrylonitrile	Amidoxine, amidrazone, oxazoline	Hg ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Zn ^{II} , Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	''	–	128
Polymethylacrylate	Hydroxamic acid	Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Cr ^{III} , Ni ^{II}	''	–	129
Poly(hydroxymethacrylate)	Thiazolidine	Cd ^{II} , Pb ^{II}	''	–	130

Abbreviations : PS–polystyrene, DVB–divinylbenzene, AAS–atomic absorption spectrometry, ICP-AES–inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry, GF-AAS–graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry, PVC–poly vinyl chloride, HG-AAS–hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometry, DCPES–direct current plasma emission spectrometry, CV AAS–cold vapour atomic absorption spectrometry, NAA–neutron activation analysis.

4.1. Applications of azo functionalized resins having phenolic-OH group : The resin having 1-nitroso - 2-naphthol as an active group was used by Ghosh and Das¹² for the selective separation of Pd^{II} and U^{VI} with exchange capacities of 0.67 and 0.43 mmol g⁻¹ respectively. Separation of Pd^{II} was based on the observation that at pH 1.0 appreciable amount of Pd^{II} was sorbed on the resin column, where other metals are not sorbed at all. At pH 5.9 most of the metal ions are sorbed along with U^{VI} which might be eluted with 0.5 M Na₂CO₃. The resin is useful particularly for the estimation of U^{VI} in sea water.

They also described the use of the resin containing 2-nitroso-1-naphthol¹³ and the exchange capacities of the metal ions like Hg^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II}, V^V, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II} were examined. It was found that the values are high for Pd^{II}, Cu^{II}, Hg^{II} and U^{VI} with a capacities of 0.93 mmol g⁻¹ for Pd^{II} at pH 1.0, 0.87, 0.98 and 1.2 mmol g⁻¹ for Cu^{II}, Hg^{II} and U^{VI} respectively, in the pH range 5.5–6.0. Separation of Pd^{II} was achieved by taking the advantage that at pH 4.5 no Pd^{IV} was sorbed and hence complete separation of these two metals is possible.

Salicylic acid anchored Amberlite XAD-2 was used by Saxena *et al.*¹⁶ for Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} recovery. The resulting chelating resin is very selective for those metals having the maximum capacities of 0.018 and 0.002 mmol g⁻¹ respectively. They applied the proposed method by taking the chelating resin in a column and passing well water through it at pH 5.0 at a flow rate of 2–5 ml min⁻¹. The metals thus sorbed were eluted by 1–2 M HCl with a recovery of 98% (RSD 6%) and 100% (RSD 3.2%) for Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} respectively.

Lee *et al.*²⁰ used the resin containing 4-(2-thiazolylazo) resorcinol (TAR) for the trace preconcentration of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II} and Mn^{II} with exchange capacities of 0.81, 0.36, 0.32, 0.27, 0.27 and 0.05 mmol g⁻¹ respectively, at pH 5.4. Except Cu^{II} and Co^{II}, most of the metal ions were recovered quantitatively (96%) by elution with 10 ml 1–2

M HNO₃ at a flow rate of 0.2 ml min⁻¹. Desorption of Cu^{II} was completed by using 2 M HNO₃ with 98.8% recovery at a flow rate 0.08 ml min⁻¹. But 100% recovery of Co^{II} was not possible due to oxidation of Co^{II} to Co^{III} and subsequent formation of Co^{III}-TAR complex.

The same group of workers also used TAR containing resin for the separation of U^{VI}⁹². The resin was packed in a mini-column and the solution of different geological standards were allowed to pass through it after maintaining the pH at 5.4 along with complexing agents such as 1,2-diaminocyclohexane-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetic acid (CDTA) and NH₄F. In this condition only U^{VI} was sorbed and the other ions were not. The retained U^{VI} was completely eluted by 10 ml 0.2 M HNO₃ with a standard deviation < 5% in all cases.

Chloromethylated-PS functionalized with pyridylazone-naphthol (PAN)²¹ was very effective for the collection of Au^{III}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Cr^{III}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} with the distribution co-efficient (log *K_d*) values in the range 2.5–7.9. The method has been applied for the preconcentration of the above metals from tap, river and natural water, human urine, milk and from ores with a recovery of 95–99%.

Pyrocatechol immobilized Amberlite XAD-2 was used by Tewari and Singh²⁶ and the exchange capacities are 0.040, 0.023, 0.092, 0.073, 0.053, 0.028 mmol g⁻¹ for Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}, respectively. The average recovery was found to be 97 to 100% with a RSD of 1.4 to 2.1%. The method has been found to be useful for the separation of these metals from river, tap water and from vitamin tablets.

o-Aminophenol anchored Amberlite XAD-2 was used by Kumar *et al.*²⁷ for the separation of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pb^{II} with exchange capacity values of 0.053, 0.030, 0.056, 0.055, 0.045 and 0.016 mmol g⁻¹ respectively. These metals are desorbed with 4 M HNO₃ with 91–98% recovery.

Kumar *et al.*²⁸ also reported the use of Tiron anchored Amberlite XAD-2 for the preconcentration of trace transition metals including uranium from river water and well water with exchange capacities of 0.22, 0.085, 0.11, 0.22, 0.054, 0.15, 0.098 and 0.032 mmol g⁻¹ for Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III} and U^{VI} respectively in the pH range 4.0–6.0. Common electrolytes did not interfere in the sorption step. All the metals can be desorbed simultaneously by 4 M HNO₃ or HCl with 91–99% recovery (RSD ≤ 8%). The limits of detection were found to be 2.0, 1.3, 5.0, 4.0, 24.0, 0.5, 2.5 and 5 ng ml⁻¹ for Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II} and Fe^{III}, respectively.

Quinalizarin anchored Amberlite XAD-2²⁹ was used for trace recovery of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} with the capacity of 0.05, 0.015, 0.027, 0.025, 0.02 and 0.017 mmol g⁻¹, respectively, in the pH range 5.7–7.0. The river water was passed through the column containing the modified resin at the desired pH and desorbed simultaneously all the metals by 2–4 M HNO₃ (RSD ≤ 6.5%).

Pyrogallol immobilized Amberlite XAD-2³⁰ can also serve as a trace metal preconcentrator. The loading capacities 0.041, 0.020, 0.046, 0.051, 0.016, 0.032, 0.046, 0.036 and 0.012 mmol g⁻¹ were obtained for Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III} and U^{VI}, respectively, at the pH range 5.5–7.0. The retained metal ions can be simultaneously desorbed by 2–4 M HNO₃ or HCl with an average recovery of 90–99% from river water (RSD ≤ 7%) and well water (RSD ≤ 8%).

Mondal *et al.*³¹ used polystyrene-DVB functionalized with 2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid (NDSA) for the speciation of chromium. The important feature of this method is that it can selectively sorb Cr^{VI} at pH 1.5 while Cr^{III} at pH 6.0 leading to the complete separation of the above species. The maximum exchange capacity for the resin was found to be 1.18 and 0.40 mmol g⁻¹ for Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} respectively. The method has been used for the speciation of chromium in natural water by column separation with a recovery of 98.5% (RSD 3%) at 95% confidence interval.

The azo groups supply N chelator and phenolic-OH supplies O donor which make the resin (N,O) donors and should be selective for transition metal ions. It can be found from the above discussions that most of the resins were selective for transition metal ions and thus it can be thought that the active group containing phenolic-OH if anchored by azo function, should be selective for transition metals.

4.2. Applications of azo functionalized resins containing heterocyclic N donor sites : Chattopadhyay *et al.*³² applied a resin containing imidazole moiety for the separation

of Hg^{II} and Ag^I from waste water. They found the exchange capacities are 0.62 and 0.75 mmol g⁻¹ respectively for the two metals at pH 6.0. Recovery was quantitative and satisfactory.

Das *et al.*⁹³ reported the use of resin containing imidazole moiety and used it for the separation of Pd^{II} and Ag^I from geological and medicinal samples. The maximum exchange capacities for Pd^{II} at pH 5.5 to 6.5 is 0.67 mmol g⁻¹ and for Ag^I 1.49 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 4.0–5.0. The sorbed Pd^{II} was desorbed by 12 M HCl and Ag^I by 5% thiourea in 0.5 M HClO₄ with an average recovery of 100% and 98%, respectively.

Sequential separation of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} from each other and from biological samples by the use of imidazolylazo resin was claimed by Mondal *et al.*⁹⁴. They found the exchange capacities to be 0.94 and 0.60 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 5.0 for Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} respectively. Taking the resin in a short column, solutions containing Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were allowed to sorb and then Cu^{II} was first eluted by 1 M neutral sulphosalicylic acid (SSA) followed by Zn^{II} by 1 M HCl with a recovery of 100–101%.

The resin, resulting from the functionalization of polystyrene-DVB with benzimidazole³³, is much more selective for heavy metals like Ag^I, Pd^{II} and Hg^{II} due to the presence of heterocyclic N atom and the exchange capacities are 1.00, 0.83 and 0.62 mmol g⁻¹ for the respective metals in the pH range 4–6. For the desorption of Ag^I and Hg^{II}, 5% thiourea in 0.1 M HClO₄ was required, whereas for Pd^{II} 12 M HCl was used with an average recovery of 98–100%. The method was applied for the quantitative separation of Ag^I and Pd^{II} from geological samples and Hg^{II} from waste water.

Polystyrene-DVB modified with 6-mercapto purine was also used by Mondal *et al.*³⁴. Hg^{II} and Ag^I were quantitatively retained at pH 6.0 with the exchange capacities 1.74 and 0.52 mmol g⁻¹ respectively. The retained metals were eluted from the column bed with 10% thiourea in 0.1 M HClO₄ with an average recovery of 99%. The limits of detection of the method were found to be 0.02 and 29 ng ml⁻¹ for Hg^{II} and Ag^I, respectively. This method has been applied for the removal of Hg^{II} from waste water and separation of Ag^I from pharmaceutical samples.

The same resin is also selective for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with exchange capacities of 1.48, 0.52 and 0.33 mmol g⁻¹, respectively, in the pH range 5.5–6.0⁹⁵. The metals are sequentially separated from biological samples by using 1 M neutral SSA for Cu^{II}, 5% thiourea in 1 M HClO₄ for Cd^{II} and 1 M HCl for Zn^{II} with a maximum error of 8.4%.

Mondal *et al.* described the speciation of chromium using the same resin⁸⁷. At lower pH, the nitrogen atom is protonated and subsequently sorbed Cr^{VI} and at higher pH the sorption of Cr^{III} was due to chelating by azo group and N-7 of purine moiety. The present method was applied in the effluent of the tannery industries.

Banerjee *et al.*³⁵ separated V^{IV} and V^V from natural water by using a chelating resin containing imidazole 4,5-dicarboxylic acid. The exchange capacities of V^{IV} and V^V were found to be 0.45 and 1.57 mmol g⁻¹, respectively at pH 3.0. Speciation studies have been carried out by sorbing both the species by column method followed by sequential elution with 0.1 M malonic acid for V^{IV} and 0.15 M NaOH for V^V.

If the active group contains a heterocyclic N donor atom, it should be selective for 'class b' metals. Thus in order to separate class b metals, azo functionalized resins containing heterocyclic N donor atom may be used.

4.3. Applications of resins anchored by -CH₂- group : Nitrosoresorcinol anchored polystyrene resin³⁸ was used for the separation of Fe^{III} and Co^{II} from each other by sorbing the above metals at pH 4.0 in a short column using a flow rate of 2.5 ml min⁻¹. The retained Fe^{III} was eluted first by 35 ml 0.01 M oxalic acid followed by 3 M HCl for Co^{II}.

The resins containing thiazole and thiazoline³⁹ are very much effective for Hg^{II} separation with an exchange capacity of 2.8 mmol g⁻¹ at pH range 1–5. One litre of sea water was passed through at pH 1.0 and the sorbed Hg^{II} was recovered from the column using 0.1 M HCl containing 5% thiourea.

The resin containing phenylalanine was used by Sugii *et al.*⁴⁰. They claimed that this resin is highly selective for Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} in the pH region 2–3. In the column method Cu^{II} can be separated from Ni^{II} and Co^{II} and may be used for the preconcentration of these metals from sea water.

Separation of precious metals like Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Ru^{III} and Rh^{III} by the use of a chelating resin containing anthranilic acid azide moiety was described by Siddhanta and Das⁴¹. The exchange capacities were found to be 0.85, 0.60, 0.20 and 0.60 mmol g⁻¹ for Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Ru^{III} and Rh^{III} respectively at pH 6.0. The metals are separated by sorbing all the ions in a short column at a flow rate of 1.5 ml min⁻¹ followed by sequential elution. At first Pd^{II} was eluted by 130 ml of 4 M HCl and then Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} by 150 ml of 6 M HCl. At last Pt^{IV} was eluted by 150 ml of 11 M HCl with recoveries of 99.5–100%.

Sugii *et al.*⁴² applied a chelating resin containing triazoethiol and used it for the separation of Ag^I and Hg^{II} with exchange capacities of 7.56 and 3.23 mmol g⁻¹ at pH

7.0. The sea water was preconcentrated in a short column at a flow rate of 20 ml min⁻¹. The retained Ag^I and Hg^{II} were eluted by 0.1 M HCl containing 1–10% thiourea and subsequently measured by AAS with an average recovery of 99.9%.

The resin containing piperazine as active group was found to be selective for Cu^{II}⁴³. The maximum capacity, 2.4 mmol g⁻¹ was achieved at pH 3–10.5. At this pH, alkali or alkaline earth metals are not chelated or retained.

The resin containing histidine moiety⁴⁴ is highly selective for Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ag^I and Co^{II} with exchange capacities of 2.06, 1.55, 1.50, 1.33, 1.24 and 1.06 mmol g⁻¹ respectively at pH 5.5. The above metals are eluted by 2 M HCl with 95–100% recoveries.

Chloromethyl polystyrene-DVB functionalized with a series of amino pyrazolone groups were used by Todorova *et al.*⁴⁵ for the recovery of precious metals. The resin exhibits selective properties towards Pd^{II}, Ag^I and Au^{III} at pH 1.0 with exchange capacities of 0.56, 0.30 and 0.30 mmol g⁻¹ respectively. The sorbed metal ions were quantitatively recovered using mineral acids or complexing agents.

Phenol-formaldehyde resin anchored with 8-hydroxyquinoline⁴⁷ was found to chelate Cu^{II} selectively at ng level with a capacity of 1.74 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 3.0. In the column operation Cu^{II} can be separated from various synthetic mixtures by sorbing the metal ions in that column at pH 3.0 under a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. The retained Cu^{II} was separated by elution with 3 M HCl under flow injection manifold, where preconcentration was performed on-line prior to detection.

The resin containing thiol and alcoholic-OH⁵¹ are highly selective for Cu^{II} over Cd^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} at pH 5.6. At higher pH, the sorption of Cu^{II} gets higher with a maximum distribution coefficient (log K_d) of 4.91 as a result of the deprotonation of amino groups which are involved in chelation.

Mondal *et al.*⁵² used bis-(*o*-aminophenyl)disulphide anchored chelating resin which is more selective for different species of arsenic due to the presence of S and N donor sites. Both the forms of arsenic viz. As^{III} and As^V were strongly sorbed by the column packed with the above resin at pH 5.5 with exchange capacities of 0.016 and 0.013 mmol g⁻¹, respectively. Complete desorption of both As^{III} and As^V took place by 1 M HCl with a recovery of 98%.

Mondal *et al.*⁵³ described an interesting method for the speciation of organic and inorganic mercury by using the chelating resin containing 1,2-bis-(*o*-aminophenylthio)ethane moiety with high selectivity and fast equilibration

rate. These features enable it to be applied for the rapid preconcentration and speciation of mercury from natural water. The separation of methyl mercury and inorganic mercury has been carried out by sorbing both the species in a column containing the chelating resin and then sequentially eluted by 75% ethanol for organic mercury and 10% thiourea in 1 M HCl for Hg^{II} with a recovery of 98.5%. The detection limit of this method was found to be 0.09 ng ml⁻¹.

Pb^{II} was selectively sorbed by the resin containing *o*-aminothiophenyl S-acetic acid⁵⁴ due to the presence of soft basic S donor atom. The maximum exchange capacity for Pb^{II} was found to be 0.03 mmol g⁻¹ at pH range 5.5–6.0. Recovery of Pb^{II} was found to be 98.9% with a relative standard deviation of 3.5% at the 99% confidence interval with a detection limit of 40.6 ng ml⁻¹.

The resin containing adenine as an active group was used by Mondal *et al.*⁵⁵. The resulting resin are very effective for the selective separation of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with exchange capacities of 0.25 and 0.30 mmol g⁻¹, respectively, at pH 1.0. Both Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were sorbed in a resin column and then sequentially extracted by 0.5 M NaF for Zn^{II} and 1 M HNO₃ for Cd^{II} with 97.5–98.5% recoveries and 2–4% RSD. The detection limits for Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were found to be 4.4 and 9.0 ng ml⁻¹, respectively.

Saha *et al.*⁵⁶ used polystyrene functionalized with thiomethyl group for the separation of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with the exchange capacities of 0.13, 0.03, 0.008 and 0.03 mmol g⁻¹, respectively at pH 4.0. Elution was carried out by using 4 M HCl.

The resin containing dithizone⁵⁷ as chelating agent was used for the separation of Au^{III}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{IV}, Os^{IV}, Ir^{IV}, Ru^{III} and Rh^{III} with exchange capacities of 0.74, 0.68, 0.31, 0.12, 0.14, 0.14 and 0.16 mmol g⁻¹, respectively in 1 M HCl. This resin has been used for the recovery of precious metals.

A chelating resin containing mercapto and amino groups for the collection of Au^{III}, Pd^{II} and Hg^{II} along with some transition metals was reported by Zhang *et al.*⁹⁶. The method shows excellent exchange capacities of 4.55, 2.44 and 1.49 mmol g⁻¹ for Au^{III}, Pd^{II} and Hg^{II}, respectively, in 2 M HCl solution. Ag^I was also sorbed at pH 7.0 with a value of 3.69 mmol g⁻¹. The desorption of Pd^{II} was done by 2 M HCl containing 1% thiourea with a recovery of 96.5%.

Singh and Gupta⁹⁷ used diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid anchored resin for Th^{IV} recovery from sea water. The resin is very selective for Th^{IV} and In^{III} with an exchange capacity of 1.86 and 1.75 mmol g⁻¹, respectively, at pH 6.0 for both. The two ions were separated from tap water and sea water in the column method under the flow rate of 4–5

ml min⁻¹. The metals were eluted by 1 M HNO₃ and subsequently measured by EDTA titration.

4.4. Applications of resins having amide linkage : The resin containing N-phenyl hydroxamic acid⁵⁸ uses its (O, O) donor sites to complex the metal ions like Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Ti^{IV}, U^{VI} and Th^{IV}. pH plays a vital role in the sorption steps. Th^{IV} and Ti^{IV} are sorbed by the resin at pH 1.0 whereas Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III} and U^{VI} are retained at pH 4.0. Several metal ions are so strongly complexed by the hydroxamic resin that it becomes a challenge to find suitable ways of eluting the metal ions from the resin column. Cu^{II}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI} could be eluted with acidic eluents. The remaining ions required complexing agents for fast, quantitative elution like lactic acid for Ti^{IV}, oxalic acid for Fe^{III}.

Orf and Fritz⁵⁹ reported the separation of U^{VI}, Th^{IV} and Zr^{IV} by the use of a tertiary amide resin from ore samples like uraninite and carnotite. The solutions containing the above metals were injected through a resin column after adjusting the pH at 3.0. In this condition most foreign metals were not sorbed. The sorbed U^{VI} was then eluted by HClO₄ solution of pH 2.0 followed by Th^{IV} by applying HClO₄ solution of pH 0.5. At last Zr^{IV} was eluted by 1 M H₂SO₄. This resin was also used to sorb Au^{III} from aqueous HCl solution with an exchange capacity of 1.7 mmol g⁻¹. The main advantage of this method is that, Au^{III} is not reduced to Au^I or to the metal. The sorbed Au^{III} was eluted by 0.1 M NaCN and can be used for many sorption and elution cycles.

Sugii *et al.*⁶⁰ used acyl oxime functionalized resin which is highly selective for Cu^{II}. The loading capacity for Cu^{II} was found to be 2.0 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 6.0 in batch experiment. Sorbed Cu^{II} was quantitatively recovered by the use of 1 M HNO₃ or HCl.

Cystein anchored polyacrylonitrile⁶¹ was used for Ag^I, Au^{III} and Pt^{III} recovery by forming chloro complex of the metals. The resin shows high sorption capacities for Au^{III}, Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pt^{IV} with maximum values of 1.22, 0.97, 0.65 and 0.39 mmol g⁻¹, respectively. The resin column was conditioned with a 0.1 M HCl and 500 ml of a very dilute solution of the above metal ions were passed through the column at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. Pt^{IV} was first eluted from the bed by 0.5 M HCl, next Hg^{II} by 6 M HCl followed by Ag^I by 2 M HClO₄. At last Au^{III} was recovered by 0.1% thiourea in 0.1 M HCl.

Thiosalicylamide anchored polystyrene-DVB was used by Dasgupta *et al.*⁶³ for the selective separation Pt^{II} and Pt^{IV} with exchange capacities of 0.71 and 0.68 mmol g⁻¹, respectively, at pH 4.38. Pt^{II} was separated quantitatively by 0.5% KCN.

The resin containing benzoyl acetanilide⁶⁴ was very selective for Ti^{IV} with an exchange capacity of 0.14 mmol g^{-1} at pH 2.1. This resin is effective for Ti recovery from bauxite in column experiment. Ti was sorbed in a short column and then desorbed by $3 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ with 96% recovery.

Das and Das⁶⁵ used the chelating resin containing quinaldenic acid amide, which is very selective for Hg^{II} due to the presence of heterocyclic N donor atom. The exchange capacity of the resin was found to be 1.98 mmol g^{-1} at pH 5.5 in which other elements like Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Fe^{III} are negligibly sorbed. Thus Hg^{II} could be separated from waste water by taking the resin in a column at pH 6.0 and desorbing the metals by 10% thiourea in 1.0 M HClO_4 .

The chelating resin containing quinaldenic acid amide group⁹⁸ falls into the border line of soft bases region and is expected to complex with soft cations like Pt^{IV} and Pd^{II} . The maximum sorption capacities for Pt^{IV} and Pd^{II} were found to be 0.19 and 0.36 mmol g^{-1} , respectively, at pH 1.0. Both the species was sorbed in a short column at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min^{-1} . Pd^{II} was eluted by 1% DMG- CHCl_3 mixture. After its quantitative recovery, Pt^{IV} was eluted by 4 M HCl with a recovery of 99%.

The same resin was used to sorb Ag^{I} with a maximum exchange capacity value of 0.68 mmol g^{-1} , at a pH 7.6, but Au^{III} was preferentially sorbed by the resin at pH 1.0 with a maximum value of 3.92 mmol g^{-1} ⁹⁹. Thus a quantitative separation of Au^{III} from Ag^{I} was achieved by simply varying the pH of the solution. In order to desorb Ag^{I} and Au^{III} , 3 M HNO_3 and 10% thiourea in 4 M HClO_4 were used respectively with a recovery of almost 100%.

The resin¹⁰⁰ was also applied to sorb U^{VI} along with Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pb^{II} at pH 3.5 to 4.0. In order to separate U^{VI} from other elements, 10 ml 0.1 M EDTA was added to the mixture. Excess EDTA did not affect the sorption capacity of U^{VI} around pH 4.0 but suppressed the exchange capacity of other metals present in the solution. The solution was percolated after maintaining the pH at 3.5 and uranium was eluted with 3 M HNO_3 with 99.9% recovery.

The resin containing thioacetamide was used by Konar and Basu⁶⁸ for the selective complexation of Cu^{II} with a capacity of 0.85 mmol g^{-1} at pH 6.0. This metal can be separated from a number of foreign metal ions. Binary mixture of Cu–Ni was separated by sorbing both the species in a column and desorbing Ni^{II} by alcoholic DMG and Cu^{II} by $4 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$. The recovery was quantitative (99.5%).

Styles *et al.*⁶⁹ used mercaptoacetamide as active group for the determination and removal of arsenic. The sorption

of different species of arsenic is depended on the pH of the solution and it was found that As^{V} is effectively sorbed at pH 2.0, whereas As^{III} at pH 8.0. Both the species were stripped by $0.2 \text{ M NH}_4\text{OH}$ with an average recovery of 99%.

4.5. Applications of esterified resins : Dev and Rao⁷¹ modified polystyrene-DVB by *N,N*-bis-(2-hydroxyethyl) glycine (bicine) for the sorption of Cu^{II} , Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} with exchange capacities of 0.38, 0.44, 0.39, 0.42, 0.38, 0.32 and 0.40 mmol g^{-1} , respectively, in the pH range 5.5–8.0. In this method Pb^{II} was separated in the presence of various ions.

The same group of workers also modified Amberlite XAD-4 with bis-(*N,N'*-salicylidene)-1,3-propanediamine⁷² for the separation of same metals. The sorbed metal ions were eluted by 1 M HCl with a recovery of 98–101%.

Moyer and Fritz⁷⁴ used the chelating resin containing hexylthioglycolate (HTG-4) groups for selective sorption of Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} , Au^{III} and Bi^{III} . The exchange capacities were found to be 1.93, 0.99, 0.76 mmol g^{-1} for Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Au^{III} respectively at pH 1, which was maintained sufficiently acidic to avoid any interaction of the metal ions with unreacted carboxylic group in HTG-4 resin. The resin was conditioned with 20 ml of 0.1 M HClO_4 – 0.0002 M tartarate at a flow rate of 2.0 ml min^{-1} and a solution containing Bi^{III} , Ag^{I} , Au^{III} and Hg^{II} was allowed to flow through this column and the metals were sequentially eluted with 0.5, 2.0 and 6.0 M HCl . Nevertheless, Au^{III} was not eluted by this process and it was eluted by 25 ml of 10^{-3} M thiourea– 10^{-3} M HCl followed by spectrophotometric method.

Amberlite XAD-4 functionalized with 1-hydrazinophthalazine⁷⁶ is selective for Fe^{III} over Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cr^{III} . Their exchange capacities were found to be 1.32, 1.24, 0.96, 0.86, 0.85, 0.82, 0.74 and 0.62 mmol g^{-1} in the pH range 4.5–8.8. The method was applied for the separation of iron from certified samples with a good recovery of 99%.

The incorporation of 7-aza-1,4,10,13-tetrathia cyclohexadecane into poly(glycidylmethacrylate)⁷⁷ leads to a solid phase which is very selective for Ag^{I} over Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with distribution co-efficient ($\log K_d$) of 3.56 at pH 5.5–6.0. Azacrown and azathiacrown on polymerization leads to an active solid surface for trace Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} , Au^{III} and Ag^{I} recovery.

4.6. Applications of polycondensed resins : Polyacrylonitrile functionalized with 1,1-divinylidenediphosphonic acid is very efficient for the sorption of Eu^{III} ⁸². The extent of complexation is quantitative in 0.04 M HNO_3 solution and

the greater affinity by the diphosphonate ligand is due to the higher coordinating ability of the phosphoryl oxygen compared to sulphonic acid group.

The monomer of dipyritylamide on polymerization leads to a solid phase preconcentrator which is able to separate Pd^{II} and Hg^{II} from aqueous solution⁸⁴. The exchange capacities for Pd^{II} and Hg^{II} were found to be 0.14 and 0.005 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 5.5. The sorbed Pd^{II} was quantitatively recovered (99%) by a solution of 0.5 M thiourea in 1.5 M HCl (10 : 90, v/v) THF-methanol mixture whereas Hg^{II} by a solution of dimercaptosuccinic acid in (20 : 80, v/v) THF-methanol mixture.

The resin containing pyridine moiety¹⁰¹ is selective for Hg^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} at pH 1.0. The maximum sorption capacity for Hg^{II} was found to be 6.0 mmol g⁻¹ in the pH range 1–5. They explained the sorption behavior of the metal ions by forming the anionic species like HgCl₃⁻ and subsequent sorption of that species at lower pH. Similar pattern was observed for Cd^{II} and Zn^{II}. However, the resin also binds Cu^{II} at pH 4.0 with a maximum value of 10.2 mmol g⁻¹ which is very encouraging to preconcentrate these metals from sea water with a recovery of 98.7%.

5. Conclusion

From the reviewed literature, it can be observed that most of the synthetic routes involve classical technique. Only two papers^{54,55} are found in which microwave irradiation was used for the functionalization of the resin. Chelating resins are mainly used for the preconcentration and separation of trace elements in environmental, industrial and biological samples but the chemical speciation studies have been carried out only to a limited extent. Thus speciation study seems to offer unexplored opportunities that may deserve the attention of scientists concerned with special reference to environmental pollution.

It is not possible to make a critical evaluation for the usefulness of the functionalized chelating resins for the recovery of lanthanides because of limited number publications in this area^{81,82}. Although two references^{22,111} were found for the separation of Zr/Hf but unfortunately no literature was found for Nb/Ta pair. Hence, the scientists are invited to pay their attention in this area.

In conclusion, solid phase extractions using functionalized resins improve the sensitivity and reliability of determination of elements in a wide variety of samples including waste water, industrial and biological materials. More studies on microwave irradiated syntheses of chelating resins and their applications of the fast speciation analyses to measure low concentrations of metal species are eagerly awaited.

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